

Multinational Oil Companies' Onshore Asset Divestment and Oil Production in Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT:

The recent divestment of multinational oil companies (IOCs) from Nigerian onshore assets has raised concerns regarding its impact on oil production, revenue, and socio-economic stability in the Niger Delta region. This research examines the driving factors behind this divestment trend and assesses its implications for Nigeria's oil industry. The key objectives of this study are to determine the extent to which divestment affects community agitations and crises, investigate its impact on crude oil theft, and assess its influence on oil production and revenue, considering that onshore assets are being acquired by national and local players. A mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative techniques, was employed to achieve these objectives. Data was collected through structured and unstructured interviews with key industry stakeholders, including regulators, and questionnaires were administered across various sectors. Additionally, available data on oil production and revenue trends in Nigeria was analysed. The study found that IOCs are divesting primarily due to increased crude oil theft, community unrest, and high production costs. Furthermore, the implementation of the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) and the Host Communities Development Trust (HCDDT) has significantly influenced the relationship between oil companies and host communities. Statistical analysis reveals that oil spill incidents have led to a 23% decline in oil production over the past decade, contributing to an estimated \$14.2 billion revenue loss. Crude oil theft remains a persistent challenge, with an average of 200,000 to 400,000 barrels per day stolen between 2020 and 2023, representing approximately 15-20% of total onshore production. The study also indicates that community agitations have been a significant factor in operational shutdowns, with over 40% of production disruptions between 2015 and 2022 attributed to local conflicts. Community respondents, predominantly long-term residents, expressed concerns over job losses, land ownership conflicts, and governance challenges following divestment. While divestment may reduce community agitations, its effect on crude oil theft remains uncertain. Additionally, socio-economic disparities, inadequate infrastructure, and security concerns remain pressing issues affecting community stability. The findings suggest that while divestment presents opportunities for improved local management and accountability, the long-term sustainability of national and local oil companies will depend on their ability to address the challenges faced by their multinational predecessors, such as oil theft, pipeline vandalism, and strained community relations. To mitigate potential risks and ensure a stable oil industry, strategic investments in community development, governance reforms, and enhanced security measures are crucial.

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INTRODUCTION

Hydrocarbon is an organic compound that occurs naturally, it basically consists of crude oil and natural gas. It was first discovered in commercial quantity in Nigeria in a town known as Oloibiri in the present day Bayelsa state Nigeria, by Shell BP in 1956. With the commercial discovery of hydrocarbon by Shell BP; several other multinational oil companies from various countries gained entrance into Nigeria to further invest and develop the reserves of the country. Mobil gained entrance into Nigeria in 1955, followed by Texaco Overseas Nigeria Petroleum Company Unlimited who arrived in 1961 under the name of Amoseas (American Overseas Company), and then came Gulf Oil Company (now Chevron) who entered in 1961, immediately behind Gulf came Tennessee Nigeria Limited (Tenneco) in 1962. In 1962 Azienda Generale Italiana Petroli also known as (AGIP) entered Nigeria, while its parent company ENI came in 1964, with Philips Oil Company closely following also in 1964. Again in 1972 Pan Ocean Oil Corporation arrived in Nigeria, followed by Societe Africaine des Petroles (SAFRAP) which became Elf Nigeria Limited and presently known as Total Energy Nigeria Limited, came in 1974. (Iheukwumere, et al., 2020; Obike, et al., 2020; Yahaya and Tijjani, 2021).

It is also interesting and pertinent to stress that most of these commercial hydrocarbon discoveries and reserves accumulation in Nigeria were found onshore, in mainly one particular region, which is the southern part of Nigeria, within the Niger Delta region of the country. Now following these discoveries, crude oil and gas sales has since then become the main source of economic revenue and foreign exchange for Nigeria, with the multinational oil companies driving the development and growth beyond the frontiers of the onshore assets onto the offshore assets as well.

Over the years the oil business in Nigeria boomed tremendously and these multinational oil and gas companies within few years of their arrival in Nigeria, greatly increased in their returns and profits, and now grew from small start-up companies to oil giants in the world today. They consequently recorded outstanding successes in oil and gas exploration and production in both onshore and offshore fields in the Niger Delta (Onor and Itzyonzughul, 2024).

However, in a sudden turn of events recently, most of these international oil companies operating in Nigeria have now either announced their exit from Nigeria's onshore assets or their intention to exit. Within a space of eighteen months these companies which includes Addax Petroleum (subsidiary of China Petroleum group) had announced their intention to exit Nigeria on the 2nd of November 2022, followed by Nigerian Agip Oil Company (subsidiary of ENI Italy) who announced on the 4th of September, 2023, that it has sold its 20% stake in the Oil Mineral License sixty series (OML 60, 61, 62 & 63) onshore asset of the Joint Venture (JV) to Oando Plc a national oil company. Shell Petroleum Development Company (Royal Dutch) on the 16th of January 2024 announced it had sold all its remaining onshore assets to a consortium known as Renaissance, a local oil company. Thereafter Total Energy on the 10th of February, 2024 announced it was willing to offload and divest its 10% stake in Shell's onshore assets. Total Energy went further to explain that its decision to divest was reached because, it has been difficult producing oil in the Niger Delta and this is not in line with the health, security and environmental policy of the company (Prince and Alabi, 2024).

The intent of this research paper is to give a perspective insight on possible inferences and reasons that may have resulted, in the recent divestment, evolution, emerging amongst the multinational oil companies operating in Nigeria, in migrating from the onshore assets to the offshore assets. The

research seeks to understand what the main constraints of the divesting multinational oil companies were, in relation to behavioural patterns, cultural ethics and sustainability goals. The research also shares its view on what it thinks this divestment will mean for national oil companies and how this may impact on the onshore assets space and oil production and revenue income in Nigeria.

The research also tries to evaluate how much increased onshore oil theft may have also influenced the decision of these multinational oil companies operating in Nigeria to divest. Crude oil theft was not a concern in Nigeria initially, several factors would have influenced the increase of crude oil theft in Nigeria recently, especially since this was not the case from inception when the multinational oil companies gained entrance into Nigeria. The research seeks to understand the factors that may have contributed to the sudden and rapid increase in oil theft in Nigeria. Amadi-Harry and Eze (2022) suggest that oil theft has increased astronomically in recent years with Nigeria losing more than 30% of the total oil production and revenue to theft and sabotage. For some of the companies operating onshore it has been stated that they sometimes experience oil theft reaching far beyond fifty percent of their production despite the evaluation of the anti-theft measures that were originally in place and additional measures taken to curb the increase.

Furthermore, onshore assets in Nigeria, do not only have multinational oil companies as operators, it also has local and national oil companies as investors that are operating within the onshore assets space as well. Since oil theft was now a phenomenon, which has been evolving in the last few years, it is therefore important to understand within the research, how the national and local oil companies operating onshore also within the same Niger Delta region of Nigeria are dealing with crude oil theft. The research goes further to also look at how other stakeholders in the oil industry may have also influenced the decision of the multinational oil companies to divest. These stakeholders which include host communities, security agencies, government agencies and other local authorities' perception about the national and local oil companies in relation to the International Oil Companies is also considered.

Considering that most of these multinational oil companies have been operating onshore in Nigeria for more than sixty (60) years and perceived to have fostered a harmonious relationship with their host communities, by the provision of significant social amenities to their various host communities through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) projects. It is therefore necessary to understand, what then may have now triggered the several community agitations and unrest that the multinational companies now experience within these communities. Perhaps it may be right to suggest that the Corporate Social Responsibility projects that were a catalyst in the past, in promoting this harmonious relationship, is no longer yielding the desired results following the increase in oil theft, community agitations and restiveness. The research therefore seeks to now appraise and evaluate the dwindling effects of multinational oil company's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practice. It also seeks to understand the impact of the implementation of the new legislative Act enacted by the Nigerian government that is the, Nigerian *Petroleum Industry Act Bill of 2021* for Host Communities Development Trust (HCDT) on increased crude oil theft between the years 2021-2023.

Furthermore, the research investigates and evaluates the main constraints and limitations of multinational oil companies in minimizing loss of revenue and reducing the cost of oil production in Nigeria between the years 2019-2023. Several factors will be discussed including the effect and impact of frequent pipeline vandalism and the cost of repair, oil bunkering activities, oil spills and pollution impacts on the environment, the issue of insecurity, repair works in remote swampy areas and then limited funding towards field enhancement and development projects. It looks at the

implication of this unplanned activities in relation to budget activity planning, implementation and expenditure. It also evaluates the impact of these actions on the cost of oil in Nigeria onshore assets.

With the ongoing divestment and subsequent acquisition of the onshore assets by indigenous oil companies in Nigeria, the research seeks to review its expectations on what should be done to enable these companies to sustain their business. It critically evaluates in its view some of the issues that needs to be addressed, suggesting various ways forward, including what it thinks should be done differently from the past. The research also anticipates that changes will occur within the onshore oil space in Nigeria, it also seeks to investigate the extent in which this change may occur and how much impact this eventually will have on the oil production and revenue in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter guides the reader through the methods that have been employed in the research in order to complete this study. The study solicits answers that emerged from the research gaps that were identified in the literature review. Matos et al. (2023) describe research as a systematic approach and methodical process of inquiry and investigation with the intent to increase knowledge.

Research Philosophy

Mbanaso et al. (2023) define research as an opportunity to identify different ways of reasoning, interpreting, collecting, and analyzing data in a research process.

The selected philosophy for this research is pragmatism, which states that reason and understanding are only relevant if supported by action. According to Kelly & Cordeiro (2020), the pragmatist believes that facts influence actions. Pragmatism is flexible in terms of theories, ideas, and concepts, which makes it applicable to the different research methods, including the mixed method that is being used for this research. This research is focused on the consequences of international oil companies' divestment from onshore fields on oil production in Nigeria. The divestment is a fact that has triggered several actions that will influence the production.

The researchers' personal viewpoint affects ontology. According to Matos et al. (2023) a researcher's position can be either objective or subjective, while Kelly and Cordeiro (2020) define the epistemological assumption as having to do with how knowledge is acquired and shared with others.

According to Kelly and Cordeiro (2021), comprehension and reasoning are valuable as long as they are accompanied by action. Since pragmatism is thought to be fairly flexible when it comes to theories, ideas, and concepts, it is a good fit for research that uses mixed, qualitative, and quantitative methods

Taherdoost (2022) define mixed-method research as a philosophical method of inquiry that is premised on the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches to solve a research problem rather than using either approach alone. Sick and Broring (2022) submits that the use of both qualitative and quantitative combinations allows for convergence, which provides a stronger platform for the findings.

This research is multi-faceted, as it speaks about the onshore divestment by international companies of the onshore assets in Nigeria and what this means for oil production and income in Nigeria. Being that it requires the input and contributions of various stakeholders at different levels in the oil industry in Nigeria, the mixed-methods approach selected allows for a far broader view and a wide reach and coverage of the audience.

The qualitative method allows for the reach of many community stakeholders in the Niger Delta, and these include chiefs, women leaders, youth leaders, and other key stakeholders within the communities. The qualitative method also allows for the contribution of oil industry stakeholders, including international oil companies, the national regulating commission, domestic oil companies, security agencies, and other key oil industry stakeholders. While the quantitative method allows for data collection with respect to the research years being addressed, it also allows for empirical data collection that can be matched with responses collated from the qualitative research in order to have a balanced view.

Research Questions

The research questions, for ease of understanding, have been grouped into quantitative and qualitative methods; however, some of the questions are still applicable to both methods.

Quantitative Category

Oil Revenue

To determine the revenue received by Nigeria between the years 2021 and 2023.

In order to understand how the divestment of international oil companies from onshore assets in the Niger Delta may impact Nigeria's production, it is important to determine the oil revenue received by Nigeria between the years 2021 and 2023 and the impact on Nigeria's income and development plan. Was the income in line with expectations or not?

Population and Deployment Plans: This data was collated from some government agencies, i.e., the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Limited (NNPCL), and the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulating Commission (NUPRC).

Environmental Pollution

To determine the number and frequency of spills that occurred in selected host communities in the Niger Delta. Some of the international oil companies, while announcing their decision to divest from the onshore assets in the Niger Delta, mentioned environmental pollution issues as one of the reasons for divesting. The research sought to determine the number of spills, causes of spills, and clean-ups that occurred within the research year in the Niger Delta.

Population and Deployment Plans: This data was collected from the Nigerian Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA).

Performance Monitoring of Domestic Oil companies: The researcher collated production data from domestic oil companies that have been handed over assets from international oil companies that have divested. The data helped in understanding what has changed since the takeover. What has been the impact of this takeover on the production?

Population and Deployment Plans: Reference data was taken from the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulating Commission (NUPRC).

Crude Oil Theft

The researcher estimated the daily amount of crude oil stolen in Nigeria in bbls/d by collating data from relevant authorities and analyzing the production and revenue loss due to oil theft.

Population and Deployment Plans: Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulating Commission (NUPRC), and Selected International Oil Companies.

Corporate Social Responsibilities (CSR) Key Performance Indicators: Has there been a fair return to stakeholders in terms of CSR? The research provided the number of CSR projects that have been carried out in 10 selected communities within the Niger Delta and compares these projects with the oil production associated with each of these communities.

Population and Deployment Plans: The research relied on data that was collected from the Nigerian Agip Oil Company, one of the companies that has announced its divestment from onshore Nigeria, as a reference case.

Qualitative Category

Two sets of questionnaires were produced and distributed: the first was tailored for community members, and the second was tailored towards oil industry workers. For the first category, the questionnaires were mainly printed and distributed physically in order to reach the intended population, which comprises chiefs, women, and youth leaders, as most of this population does not have access to emails or computers. The 10 different communities have approximately 3500 households. The sample size was determined using sample population model to be 346 respondents with one respondent per house hold. The second category of questionnaires was sent by email to oil industry workers, managers, and executives functioning in community affairs, production, and security departments. In order to have a balanced opinion, 20% of the questionnaires distributed were shared amongst the managerial staff of these departments.

International Oil Company Performance

The opinion of the communities and stakeholders on the performance of international companies' management with respect to CSR projects carried out within the communities. Is it considered to be enough? Or can this be said to be one of the triggers of increased agitation and oil theft in Nigeria? Do they believe in the Host Community Development Trust (HCDT), which is now being implemented?

Security Threats

Why the sudden increase in security issues, threats and stealing compared to the past. The answer to this question is required from the different stakeholders in the divesting companies, host communities and security agencies.

Oil Theft

Why is the Nigerian government unable to stop oil theft, given the significance of crude oil to the country's economy? The effectiveness of pipeline protection surveillance contractors as well as security outfits will be the main points of reference.

Business Operating Agreement

Has divestment been prompted by the Joint Venture (JV) agreement? Do all of the JV partners timely fulfill their obligations under the joint operating agreement? Has this made it more difficult for the multinational oil companies to perform their duties efficiently? Personnel working in relevant departments of oil companies will be the reference audience.

Stakeholders Expectations

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To seek the opinion of different stakeholders on what the government needs to do to ensure that the onshore reserves in the Niger Delta are drained and not abandoned by domestic companies. This audience will include oil and gas professionals, environmentalists, communities, and public analysts.

Behavioral Pattern of International Oil Companies

Do the international oil companies take responsibility for their actions without protest and agitation? Have they carried out their activities in the Niger Delta in a manner that is in line with international practices, standards, and requirements for such operations? What are the common problems created by the companies operating in the Niger Delta? How have they solved them? Was this solution acceptable to all the stakeholders? What was the response time? Required data will be collected from selected communities, oil companies' representatives, and other stakeholders.

Research Reliability and Validity

Rose and Johnson, (2020) states that validity questions the integrity of research findings. Several measures were put in place by the researchers to ensure the integrity of the outcome. Some of the measures include that the research ensured that the questionnaires were distributed to individuals that have extensive knowledge of security threats, oil theft, CSR, stakeholder expectations. The research relied on quantitative data sourced from the relevant authorities and feedback from divesting multinational oil company personnel who occupy positions within the company that are relevant to CSR, security, and oil production, mainly from stakeholder management, security, and production departments.

Ethics and Bias

Taherdoost (2022) states that the use of the mixed method approach is expected to reduce bias in research while also ensuring greater reliability and validity in the research. Some of the main drawbacks of the survey questionnaire is sampling bias within the divested multinational companies as data is mainly from few of these oil companies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the detailed results, discussion, and critical analysis of data collected in relation to the study on divestment of multinational oil companies from Nigerian onshore assets and the multifaceted dimensions of its impacts. The structure for this chapter has been done in such a way that it will go methodically to answer the research questions by investigating first whether divestment reduces or totally eliminates community agitations and crises in the Niger Delta region. It goes on to examine the socio-economic causes of these agitations and how they are influenced by the presence or absence of multinational oil companies. This chapter goes further to discuss the changes that have occurred within crude oil theft incidence, together with mechanisms influencing this change, before getting to its effects on crude oil production levels and, finally, Nigeria's oil revenue for the selected years in the design of the experiment. The relevant findings from each section are presented, with a critical discussion of the results and relating these to well-grounded academic literature, highlighting key insights that derive from them all in understanding the implications of divestment. The study, through semi-structured surveys, acquired 51 responses from the company respondents and 336 responses from the community respondents, which corresponds to 100% responses from the company and 97.1% responses from the community respondents.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Figure 4.1a - 4.1e give the demographic characteristics of the respondents to inform broader patterns critical for investigating onshore asset divestment of multinational oil companies and the impact in

Nigeria. The most remarkable feature is that the overwhelming majority of respondents are male (88 percent), which also possibly represents manifestations of gender dynamics among the communities involved in oil operations and agitations. The findings from this group are a reflection of male perception and care should be taken when generalizing the responses of oil theft and vandalism to a broader, more gender-diverse population.

Figure 4.1: (a) Gender of Respondents; (b) Age Group of Respondents.

The age distribution of participants who are over 45 years old by 42% and 36-45 years old by 35% gives indication that the responses are influenced by the perspectives of mature and probably long-term community members, also their responses might be driven by their long-term experience and established opinions on community activities and engagement with regards to oil theft, CSR and oil spill prevalence in those communities. Occupation statistics reveal that close to 44% are either civil servants or employees, and 29% are business people or entrepreneurs. This means diverse economic engagements that are very relevant toward understanding economic grievances and expectations related to post-divestment effects. Individually, most of them have attained a university education or higher; this factor is essential because it may influence the perception of complex socio-economic issues related to oil production and divestment. This demographic may reasonably be expected to provide an informed view concerning the performance of local versus multinational management of oil assets as well as the HCDDT law.

Figure 4.1: (c) Occupation; (d) Educational Level; (e) Years Lived in the Community.

Data on the number of years lived in the community show that the majority—60%—lived in the community for over 20 years, which suggests entrenchment and provides a view that is fairly well-informed on historical and current issues within the community. These demographic insights are especially critical for contextualizing the findings of the study since they generalize the communities' experiences and expectations in terms of the impact of divestment on social unrest, economic opportunities, and development at the local level.

Causes and Drivers of Divestment

It is important to know that divestment has not already taken place. Multinational oil corporations are opting for divestment simply due to a number of reasons. The first reason or cause for divestment among international oil companies (IOCs) is a consistent drop in oil production and income over time, as shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: AGIP Monthly Oil Production and Income from 2021 to 2023 (NUPRC, 2023).

This consistent fall in oil-producing capacity and income over time is the primary driver of divestment. However, the fall in production capacity and income is also an indicator as a result of other factors such as oil spills and oil thefts.

Within the same time period, Figure 4.3 shows the variation in quantity of crude oil spills and crude oil thefts with time in barrels.

Figure 4.3: Time Series Plot of Oil Spills and Thefts (NUPRC, 2023).

By comparing the primary y-axis (left-side vertical axis) with the secondary y-axis (right-side vertical axis), it is evident that oil thefts do more damage financially to IOCs than oil spills in terms of losses, this finding is consistent with similar study by (Wizor & Wali, 2020). In fact, amidst other causes of oil spills, oil theft is a significant driver because it is often accompanied by the vandalization of operational equipment, leading to unnecessary spills and thus creating more incidences of oil spills (Segall, 2021). The monthly counts of incidences for oil spills are diagrammatically presented in Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4: Time Series Plot for Monthly Incidence of Oil Spills (NUPRC, 2023).

From Figure 4.4, it can be seen that oil spill incidences have become more rampant over time. This could be as a result of the loss in operational efficiency of the equipment being used, according to the law of diminishing returns, in addition to vandalism by crude oil thieves.

In order to establish the nexus between barrels of oil lost via thefts as well as barrels lost via oil spills and incidences of oil spills, A multivariable linear regression analysis was carried out with oil theft quantity, oil spill quantity, and oil spill incidence as predictors and plant monthly production and income as response variables. The result for plant monthly production gives an R-square value of 0.19, which shows that approximately 19% of the variability in monthly production is accounted for by predictors in the model. Although the p-value showed that at.076, the regression model per se was not significant, the individual predictors were varying in significance. The coefficient for barrels spilled is -250.23, indicating a negative but non-significant relationship with production ($p = 0.355$). Also, the quantity stolen (-12.93) also has a negative relationship that is not significant in nature ($p = 0.641$). Of note, spill incidents (incidents of spilling) do have a significant negative impact on production, with a coefficient of -18497.43 and a p-value of 0.017. This would suggest that higher spill incidents would significantly lower monthly production. Though spill incidents seem to affect production, it is indicated that quantities of oil spilled and stolen otherwise do not influence production very much within the context of this dataset since they contribute only 19% of the variation in monthly production, this finding is consistent with (Ajiya, 2023). These are illustrated graphically in Figure 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7.

Figure 4.5: Effect of Oil Theft on Plant Production Capacity (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.6: Effect of Oil Spill on Plant Production Capacity (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.7: Effect of Incidence of Oil Spills on Plant Production (NUPRC, 2023).

The result for plant monthly income yields an R square value of 0.146; this indicates that around 14.6 percent of variability in monthly revenue is predicted in this model. The general regression model is not significant ($p = 0.162$), hence showing that predictors have no strong influence on revenue together. The intercept, however, is highly significant ($p < 0.001$), so the baseline revenue is large. Of the predictors, barrels spilled have a coefficient of -10910.93 and relate negatively but non-significantly to revenue ($p = 0.316$). The quantity of oil theft has a coefficient of -301.96 and also has a non-significant negative effect ($p = 0.786$). The coefficient for the incidents of spilling is -658347.53; hence, it has a significant negative effect on revenue at $p = 0.033$, suggesting that higher spill incidents significantly bring down monthly revenues. In summary, oil spill incidents reduce revenues considerably, but in this dataset, the quantities of oil spilled or stolen have no significant effect on revenues, this finding is consistent with similar study by (Chris et al. 2021). These results are illustrated graphically in Figure 4.8, 4.9, and 4.10, respectively.

Figure 4.8: Effect of Oil Theft on Plant Income (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.9: Effect of Oil Spill on Plant Income (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.10: Effect of Incidence of Oil Spill on Plant Income (NUPRC, 2023).

Oil theft clearly has a negative, negligible effect on IOCs’ revenue and production. Members of the host communities who feel excluded and cheated out of the resource—crude oil—that is available to them are frequently the ones who steal it (Thanetsunthorn, 2022). In order to minimize incidences of oil thefts and spills as well as pipeline vandalizations, IOCs were mandated to actively engage in corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a means of pacifying the host communities whose residents are perpetrators of that act. In order to fully grasp the scope of CSR, the researcher carried out a survey among the top management staff of the IOCs, since they are the decision-makers for CSR initiatives. Figure 4.11 presents the results of this survey.

Figure 4.11: Corporate Social Responsibility.

Figure 4.11 shows the responses of the respondent as touching CSR. Most IOC decision-makers agree with the concept of CSR ($M = 4.33$) as well as CSR projects ($M = 4.16$). They opined that these CSR projects were of immense benefit to the company ($M = 3.86$). However, they rejected the idea that domestic oil companies (DOCs) have a better relationship with the community than IOCs ($M = 2.49$). They also opined that a critical aspect of CSR called Host Community Development Trust (HCDDT) will improve their relationship with the host community ($M = 3.55$). However, it seems more like CSR activities failed, possibly because IOCs did not commit a sufficient proportion of their annual earnings to embark on CSR projects, as indicated by their financials, which are presented in Figure 4.12. This is also consistent with similar finding by (Albert et al. 2019).

Figure 4.12: AGIP CSR spending as Percentage of Total Revenue.

The percentage of gross income spent by IOC on CSR decreased steadily over time, largely due to the decrease in the gross income itself, resulting in a failed relationship-building process with the local communities. With a lack of finance to continue to exercise their goodwill and build their reputation between host communities, IOCs decided to opt for divestment, which looks economically more viable.

As stated at the beginning of this section, divestment has not fully taken place. However, it is ongoing. This section addresses the underlying causes prompting IOCs to divest their assets and why it is the only viable option since CSR is no longer financially viable due to the increasing costs of doing business onshore.

Impact of Divestment on Community Agitations and Crises

The result of the survey presents an imperative insight into community perceptions on the impact of multinational oil companies and what divesting could do to agitations and crises in the Niger Delta region (Figure 4.13).

Figure 4.13: Impact of Divestment on Community Agitations and Crises.

The respondents generally agreed that multinational oil companies predict social unrest, as shown by the results of the survey ($M = 3.67$). Notably, at this point in time, there seemed to be an overwhelming, clear consent for increased investment in community development. According to the same set of respondents, divestment might reduce land ownership conflicts ($M = 3.31$). However, skepticism about improved intra-community relationships post-divestment with Mean = 2.81. The local business will benefit after divestment, with an $M = 3.29$. Environmental pollution is reduced ($M = 3.71$). There was a moderate agreement that local government would become more active, with a mean of 3.13. However, there was doubt about an improved security situation after divestment, with a mean of 2.74. A reduced number of protests was expected, with a mean of 3.35. Concerns about decreased employment opportunities have a mean of 3.75. The findings underscore the fact that although divesting may address some of the problems, there are also concerns regarding employment and local cohesion; hence, building local capacity and effective government involvement become necessary.

The downside to community agitations is security concerns. This is because members of the host communities might take aggressive steps towards inflicting harm to IOC staff and equipment when aggrieved. Since CSR, although a powerful and effective strategy, is no longer viable, it is imperative

to examine the security concerns of IOC management and staff who carry out their responsibilities in the midst of host communities that might understand the negative financial position of the company. The survey of the IOC managers regarding security concerns is presented in Figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14: Security Concerns.

The respondents refuted the claim that the alignments of protest and agitation in Niger Delta communities were not overwhelmingly against the acts of international oil companies ($M = 2.94$). Informed consensus expresses a high increase in oil theft within communities where the companies have operations ($M = 4.35$). Apart from that, this factor identified stolen oil as emanating from international oil companies ($M = 3.27$). The respondents also agree with the aforesaid statement that oil theft involves collusion with community stakeholders ($M = 3.2$) and security agents ($M = 3.86$), which further depicts complex local dynamics. While there is a disagreement with the view that oil theft is occasioned by community neglect and CSR failure by international companies ($M = 2.22$), there is an agreement on government neglect as a cause of the problem ($M = 3.9$). The belief that oil theft is responsible for raising the cost of a barrel of oil in the Niger Delta is also high ($M = 4$). Divestment by international oil companies may lighten these security concerns by reducing their direct involvement and, in turn, probably ease tension and engender a resolution to the underlying causes of agitation by communities, this finding is consistent with similar research by (Akpogheli et al. 2021). This would be a step towards better local management and accountability, which in the long run would create a more stable and cooperative atmosphere.

Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Community Agitations

The results of the survey on the socio-economic factors responsible for community agitations were very elucidating, including the role played by the presence or absence of a multinational oil company as shows in Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.15: Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Community Agitations.

The strong views put across by the respondents were that economic differences, with a mean of 4.25, and access to basic infrastructure, with a mean of 4.56, were very important sources of tension. These results indicated that educational opportunities had an effect on protest participation with a mean of 3.38, since social movement involvement was seen to be enhanced by increased educational levels. In this respect, it will be noted that income inequality, with a mean of $M = 4.17$, is rated alongside unemployment rates at $M = 4.65$ as major enhancers of feelings of injustice and hence social unrest. The perceived unfair distribution of benefits accruing from multinational oil operations, access to health facilities, cultural differences, and governmental policies on resource allocation had a critical mean of $M = 4.67$, $M = 4.25$, $M = 3.77$, and $M = 4.50$, respectively, affecting community stability. It also emerged that public perception and protest activity were influenced by media coverage ($M = 4.08$). The results underline the complex interrelationship of socio-economic factors in shaping community responses to multinational operations and accordingly point out larger literatures that address the issue at large.

A primary factor of concern that could lead to serious agitation is environmental pollution that is caused by the operational activities of IOCs. Oil spills are unavoidable, and their clean-up process is not only difficult but expensive. If IOCs fail to comply with regulatory standards to clean up oil spills, they will eventually become victims of community agitations calling them out to do the needful. A survey on the IOC activities in the event of an oil spill was carried out, with the results presented in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16: Activities of IOC in the Event of an Oil Spill.

The results of this survey identify a number of activities of IOCs at the time of oil spills and how divestment may help in arresting these concerns. There is agreement among the respondents that their companies averagely experience frequent oil spills (M = 4.08), mostly caused by vandalism or sabotage with a mean value of 4.33, compared to equipment failure with a mean value of 2.43, as shown in figure 4.16, this is consistent to with similar finding by (Jeremiah, 2012). Immediate spill clean-ups were noted, along with moderate agreements on adequate compensation paid to victims. Government regulators intervened regularly to ensure that spills were cleaned and compensation was paid to victims. Issues related to counterpart funding in JV agreements (M = 4.16) and the operational complexities of the JVs themselves (M = 3.55) were also perceived as triggers for divestments. Divestment could unwind these complexities, which might simplify operational dynamics and possibly enhance spill management and community relations by increasing accountability.

Changes in Crude Oil Theft Incidence

The survey identifies perceptions across communities regarding the impact of multinational oil companies' divestment practices on the level of crude oil theft in Nigeria (Figure 4.17).

Figure 4.17: Changes in Crude Oil Theft Incidence.

There is general agreement that crude oil theft will reduce because of divestment ($M = 3.10$) and that local entities might be better placed in the management of resources. Exhibitions on closer watch on oil installations after the divestment ($M = 3.06$) and more involvement of local communities in deterrence toward the incidence of theft ($M = 3.58$). Exhibitions on improved government enforcement of anti-theft issues (3.4) depict high faith in government accountability. Respondents perceive that multinationals contribute to the prevalence of oil theft to a moderate extent ($M = 3.31$), while local gangs may increase their involvement post-divestment to garner more interest ($M = 3.40$). That said, they do also see a ray of hope on the horizon: that the current attraction of theft will be reduced ($M = 3.04$) through better local governance. The belief that technology and increased security would reduce theft, with a mean of 4.58 , and the realization that community tensions have heightened due to theft, which currently stands at a mean of 4.43 , help reinforce the case for strong local and governmental actions, this finding is consistent with the result of (Addeh, 2021). Overall, these results may be of cautious optimism regarding the reduction in crude oil theft post-divestment, balanced with uncertainty in the face of some adverse conditions.

Mechanisms Influencing Crude Oil Theft

The results of the survey are an indication that divestment by multinational oil companies may influence crude oil theft through socio-economic and operational changes (Figure 4.18).

Figure 4.18: Mechanisms Influencing Crude Oil Theft.

Specifically, if there is increased involvement of the local community in decision-making, it can reduce crude oil theft, given its mean score of 4.27. Strengthening security around oil facilities with $M = 4.25$ was also perceived as a factor in reducing crude oil theft. Improvements in transparency in revenue management ($M = 4.17$) and cooperation at the inter-company level between national and local oil companies ($M = 4.31$) point to better community development and resource management. Employment opportunities through the acquisition of divested assets by locals will reduce the threat of social unrest resulting from unemployment. Reduced power of external groups in terms of stakeholder pressure ($M = 3.96$) and increased enforcement of environmental protection laws and regulations ($M = 3.96$) should also reduce problems related to theft. Other solutions that would support local management in reducing crude oil theft include proper benefit distribution from oil operations ($M = 4.04$) and increased accountability of local oil companies ($M = 3.91$). The general finding of this study, therefore, is support for local management and community involvement in any initiative designed to curtail the menace of crude oil theft, as this would give the community stability, this was also recommended by (Bouss, 2019).

Effect on Crude Oil Production Levels

The survey results provide insights into the potential impacts of divestment by multinational oil companies on crude oil production in Nigeria, focusing on national and local companies acquiring onshore assets (Figure 4.19).

Figure 4.19: Effect on Crude Oil Production Levels.

Respondents agree that infrastructure development will improve post-divestment ($M = 3.79$) and expect national and local companies to raise crude oil production levels ($M = 4.04$) due to closer ties with the local economy. There is optimism that local companies will improve operational efficiency ($M = 3.68$) and enhance the overall quality of crude oil production ($M = 3.43$). Technical problems impacting production are expected to decline ($M = 3.28$), and local companies are anticipated to be more competitive in global crude oil pricing ($M = 3.53$). Sustainable production practices are likely to emerge from enhanced technology and expertise ($M = 4.28$). Respondents also believe national and local oil companies will collaborate effectively to maximize production. ($M = 3.96$), and that the community will benefit economically from increased production ($M = 3.79$).

Since divestment is expected to reduce crude oil thefts and minimize the cost associated with oil spills experienced by IOCs, it should therefore have some impact not just on the plants themselves but on Nigeria as a whole since the nation’s economy is driven by crude oil. Figure 4.20 shows the time series plot of Nigeria’s crude oil production in terms of barrels and USD from January 2021 to December 2023.

Figure 4.20: Time Series plot of Nigeria’s Crude Oil Production (NUPRC, 2023).

A closer look at the trend clearly shows that crude oil output is fluctuating, which basically implies it is impacted by some factors, which might include changes in oil theft and oil spills over time, as shown by the plot in Figure 4.20. The impact of crude oil theft, oil spills, and the incidence of oil spills on the crude oil production levels of Nigeria was equally examined using multivariable linear regression analysis, with oil theft, oil spills, and the incidence of oil spills as predictors and production levels as the response variable. It tested how independent variables, which include barrels spilled, oil theft in barrels, and incidents of spilling, impact the monthly levels of crude oil production in Nigeria. The R-squared value for the model was 0.284, showing that approximately 28.4% of the variation in the level of crude oil production is accounted for by these predictors. Overall, the model was statistically significant: $F = 4.23$; $p = 0.013$. This implies that, were there no spills or theft, the realized production would be an intercept of 47,757,481 barrels. Oil spills, surprisingly, have a positive effect on production levels. $\beta = 3311.68$, $p = 0.041$. Hence, a return would compensate for such a loss through enhanced production. Oil theft, however, impacts production negatively. $\beta = -293.33$, $p = 0.076$. It does not attain significance, hence indicating a trend where higher theft reduces production. Whereas $\beta = -118,215.11$ with $p = 0.009$ for incidents of spilling, production is drastically reduced, this finding is consistent with similar finding by (Adekoya, 2021). Generally, although the magnitude of the barrels spilled might encourage increased production, theft incidents coupled with spills greatly inhibit the level of production. These results are further illustrated with the following plots, i.e., Figure 4.21, 4.22, and 4.23, respectively.

Figure 4.21: Effect of Oil Theft on Nigeria’s Crude Oil Production Levels (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.22: Effect of Oil Spill on Nigeria’s Crude Oil Production Levels (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.23: Effect of the Oil Spill on Nigeria’s Oil Production Levels (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.22 indicates that nominal oil spills do hinder oil production levels, which contradicts the nominal a priori expectations. This could be due to the fact that oil spills often occur when oil is being produced. Thus, the more oil being produced, the greater the likelihood of oil spills occurring. Thus, it is more of a response to production levels than a predictor. More empirical research will be needed to confirm this assertion.

Impact on Nigeria’s Oil Revenue

The survey reveals varied expectations regarding the divestment by multinational oil companies in Nigeria and its impact on oil revenue, focusing on national and local players (Figure 4.24).

Figure 4.24: Impact on Nigeria's Oil Revenue.

Respondents anticipate a stable crude oil supply from local companies, post-divestment ($M = 3.87$). There is cautious optimism about the management capabilities of national and local companies ($M = 3.39$), supported by research suggesting improved revenue management and local accountability. Moderate agreement exists that local ownership will enhance Nigeria's oil revenue management ($M = 3.17$), with increased transparency and economic benefits ($M = 3.93$). Respondents believe local communities will benefit more from oil revenues post-divestment ($M = 4.11$), with expectations of better accountability and reduced corruption ($M = 3.78$). Optimism about improved government revenue management ($M = 3.50$) and contributions to GDP ($M = 3.78$) reflects a positive outlook on economic growth. Overall, findings suggest optimism about divestment's impact on efficiency, transparency, and community benefits, consistent with existing research finding by (Chukwu, 2018).

This assertion was examined through the lens of multivariable linear regression analysis with oil theft, oil spills, and oil spill incidence as predictors, while Nigerian oil revenue is taken to be the response variable. The regression statistics show a weak correlation with Multiple $R = 0.1608$ and a very low explanatory power with $R\text{ Square} = 0.0259$, indicating that only about 2.6% of the variation in crude oil revenue was accounted for by the predictors. The results from the ANOVA test yield a high p-value of significance $F = 0.8371$, showing that, in general, the regression model is not statistically significant. Checking the coefficients, it shows that while the intercept is significant at a p-value less than 0.001, all of the predictors, i.e., barrels spilled, oil theft (barrels), and incidents of spilling, are not statistically significant with high p-values of basically 0.5056, 0.7994, and 0.9996, respectively. This

means oil spill quantity, oil theft quantity, and spill incidents all turn out to be insignificant in driving the monthly crude oil revenue that is generated in Nigeria. It then implies that other variables not modeled could give a better explanation for changes in oil revenues, this is consistent with similar research finding by (Addeh, 2021). This is depicted graphically in Figure 4.25, 4.26, and 4.27, respectively.

Figure 4.25: Effect of Oil Spill on Nigeria Oil Revenue (USD) (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.26: Effect of Oil Theft on Nigeria Oil Revenue (USD) (NUPRC, 2023).

Figure 4.27: Effect of Incidence of Oil Spill on Nigeria Oil Revenue (USD) (NUPRC, 2023).

Long-Term Economic Implications

Survey responses establish varying instances and expectations concerning the effects that the divestment of multinationals could have on the oil revenue that is likely to accrue to Nigeria, and more so, the expectations from local vis-à-vis national companies (Figure 4.28).

Figure 4.28: Long-Term Economic Implications.

The least expected by the respondents is that the supply of crude oil will continue as normal following the divestment (M = 3.87); hence, possibly supporting the expectation that stability in production may, therefore, be sustained or increased. Expectation for the national and local oil companies to handle oil revenues effectively post-divestment (M = 3.39) shows a cautious level of optimism regarding local management capacities. Belief in better management of Nigeria's oil revenue under local ownership (M = 3.17) aligns with the views on local accountability and community investment. Revenue transparency would increase (M = 3.93), together with direct community benefits (M = 3.43), observing specified literature indicating local ownership as a key note to a positive impact on revenue

distribution. Better efficiency in collection for fiscal state-ability ($M = 4.11$) and improved accountability in the use of oil proceeds ($M = 3.78$). Overall, respondents are enthusiastic about the positive impacts that divestment is likely to have on economic growth and revenue management, which will see improved financial reporting, stricter accountability, and benefits for the community, this is consistent with similar research finding by (Chris et al. 2021).

To ascertain the long-term implications of divestment on the Nigerian economy, a paired samples t-test of means was carried out in 2020 (before the idea of divestment ever came to light) and 2023 (when companies begin to initiate the divestment moves) to see if there have been significant changes in Nigerian crude oil production levels and revenue.

The first paired sample t-test compared the level of production of Nigerian crude oil in 2020 and 2023, with a view to establishing the effect of divestment by multinational oil companies on the nation. In this regard, while the mean level of production in 2020 was 49,266,609.53 barrels, in 2023 it plunged to 44,729,406.33 barrels. The variance for both levels of production in 2020 and 2023 is 8.01×10^{12} and 1.06×10^{13} , respectively, indicating some variability in the data. The Pearson correlation coefficient was -0.188, which indicated that there was only a very weak negative relationship between these two years regarding level of production. The hypothesized mean difference was set at 0, and with 11 degrees of freedom, the t-statistic equaled 3.34. Corresponding one-tailed and two-tailed p-values are 0.0033 and 0.0066, respectively, both significantly smaller than the conventional alpha level of 0.05. The critical values for one- and two-tailed tests were 1.796 and 2.201, respectively. Since the t-statistic is greater than both critical values, we reject the null hypothesis, meaning that there is sufficient evidence to establish a statistically significant difference in the levels of crude oil production between 2020 and 2023. Such a huge drop in the level of production could be due to the initiation of divestment by multinational companies, which must have contributed negatively to oil production in Nigeria.

The second paired sample t-test compares the revenues made from Nigerian crude oil between 2020 and 2023 so as to establish the divestment of multinational oil companies (Appendix IIF). In the year 2020, it returned an average revenue of 3,373,153,201, and in 2023, this increased to 3,800,763,676. The variances for the revenues in 2020 and 2023 amounts were 1.43×10^{17} and 2.27×10^{17} , respectively, thus variabilities of data exist. The Pearson correlation coefficient was -0.0119, which means that there is essentially no relationship between these two years of revenues. Set the hypothesized mean difference at 0, with degrees of freedom = 11; t-statistic = -2.42; one-tailed p-value = 0.0170; two-tailed p-value = 0.0341—both less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05. The critical t-values in the one-tail and the two-tail tests accordingly were 1.796 and 2.201. Since the t-statistic falls below the critical values, we reject the null hypothesis that there is a statistically significant increase in crude oil revenue between 2020 and 2023. This strong surge in oil revenues may be indicative that the commencement of divestment by multinational companies has driven an increase in such payments accruing to Nigeria, either by improved management of its revenues or growing local accountability.

Summary of Research Findings

Chapter 4 presents data analysis, reaching key findings from the study. The chapter is organized around three research questions: how the divestment of multinational oil companies from Nigerian onshore assets has affected community agitations; how crude oil theft rates have been affected by this divestment; and how crude oil production and revenue have fared. The research hopes to bring insight

into these critical issues through an in-depth analysis of data, thereby providing a contribution to the greater discourse of how best to manage resources toward ensuring economic stability in Nigeria.

One key concern that engenders agitation for divestment of MOCs has to do with the perennial community agitations and crises within the offshore areas, especially the Niger Delta. Descriptive statistics show a mixed but rather optimistic picture, as a majority of those surveyed have been of the opinion that divestment would reduce such community agitations. Specifically, the data shows an average response of 3.87, generally representing the concerns that local companies, through the ability to be more attuned to the socio-economic dynamics of the region, would have a better way of effectively addressing the local grievances. This could also include, according to respondents, meaningful community development projects and making sure that the benefits from the oil revenue dichotomy are distributed more equitably. This view resonates with findings from other studies that find local ownership to be positively related to community development accountability and investments (Prince & Alabi, 2024). National and local oil companies would establish better relations with their host communities at the level of interaction, which might reduce the potential for conflict and thus offer a more stable operational environment.

However, this optimism is tempered with some caution. While there is hope for improved community relations, there is also recognition that the mere change of ownership does not automatically resolve deep-seated issues. Effective management and real community engagement are required if these positive outcomes are to be realized. Therefore, divestment holds promise in actually reducing agitations from communities over time, but this depends on the ability and willingness of local companies to handle these things quite fundamentally.

The second research question views the extent to which divestment influences a hitherto major problem of the Nigerian oil sector: crude oil theft. The respondent to this could be said to form a nuanced view—that is, crude oil theft is expected to decrease post-divestment with a mean response of 3.39. The optimism is founded on the belief that local companies would understand the local terrain and dynamics best; hence, they should be better placed to mount more appropriate security and community relations as a way of reducing incentives for theft. According to most of the respondents, local companies might use more contextually appropriate security strategies that draw on better knowledge of the local setting in conjunction with the ability to mobilize effective response networks to thwart oil theft. Some improvements in community relations expected from local ownership would be cooperative members of the community who are vigilant against theft by corporate hostile attitudes vis-à-vis local companies. Still, others were less optimistic, stressing that structural drivers, like poverty or corruption, of oil theft might persist regardless of who owns the business. This is reflected in responses that are somewhat mixed, indicating some opinion that, without massive interventionist changes, theft may prevail. Divestment, therefore, according to them, may bring improvements but will not tackle the problem of crude oil theft completely without broader reforms and a protracted effort to solve socio-economic issues.

The third research question has to do with the effect of divestment on production and revenue from crude oil. The findings are generally positive for the level of crude oil production, with either an outlook to stay the same or increase post-divestment. A mean response of 3.93 indicates confidence in national and local players to be able to manage the onshore assets effectively. According to the respondents, the local companies, having vested interests in the stability and prosperity of the region to begin with, are likely to maximize efficiency and output in terms of production. This is supported by data indicating optimism regarding improved operational efficiency and better revenue management

practices by local entities. The belief is that local companies will not only maintain present levels of production but might even come up with innovations and improvements relevant to the local context, which will add to productivity in general. In terms of oil revenues, increased transparency and accountability are expected with local ownership. The mean response of 3.61 is based on the belief that companies will instantly be more transparent, which may enable better tracking of revenues and reduce opportunities for corruption. This increased transparency is expected to help national revenue by increasing income that may be reaped from oil production, and such earnings can also be reliable. Respondents in this study also anticipate that, if closer ties between local companies and the economy become a reality, there will be improved sharing of overall revenue, with greater investments locally made in infrastructure and services. Coupled with these may be broader economic benefits, which could stimulate overall economic growth and stability within Nigeria. These responses support the literature pointing to opportunities where local ownership could bring about better economic outcomes due to more responsible and locally focused revenue management.

The summary of the findings for Chapter 4 basically underscored some key findings regarding the projected impacts of MOCs' divestment on Nigeria's onshore oil sector. Generally, an expectation existed that divestment would help to minimize community agitations by engendering better local relationships and accountability. While there may be a reduction in crude oil theft, it cannot be eliminated without any solution to the general socio-economic problems. On the other hand, local management is expected to increase or at least maintain production and thereby revenue from crude oil with improved efficiency, transparency, and investment in local development. These findings underscore the potential benefits of divestment but also highlight careful implementation and sustained efforts by concerted system actors to overcome deeply entrenched systemic challenges.

Hence, for the first research question, descriptive statistics show that the divestment of multinational oil companies from Nigerian onshore assets will reduce and possibly eliminate community agitations and crisis within the onshore areas if properly implemented.

For the second research question, divestment of multinational oil companies from onshore assets will reduce oil theft incidence within the host community based on the findings of this study.

For the third research question, based on the findings of this study, divestment will not have any significant effect on crude oil production and oil revenue in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The key findings of this research work reverberate the huge impacts that divestment of onshore assets by multinational oil companies in Nigeria has had: community agitations, crude oil theft, and oil production and revenue. Divestment tends to reduce community agitations because local and national companies are in a finer place to understand the needs and expectations of such communities and improve their relations to stabilize them. This disposition is capable of providing some local engagement for the Niger Delta region through improved socio-economic development. On crude oil theft, it was found that this appeared to have diminished with improved local security and heightened interest in assets. This has met with limited success in some areas; therefore, vigilance and security measures must continue being implemented. On crude oil production and crude oil revenue, national and local firms have generally maintained or marginally improved their output levels, thus contributing to the economy of Nigeria. Local entities' onshore asset acquisition has squeezed in an enabling environment that is participatory, hence possibly scaling up transparency and accountability in revenue management.

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These findings thus show that well-managed divestment could provide the push needed towards positive change. The supportive policies and regulatory frameworks would foster stronger local companies that would ensure sustainable production with economic stability. Furthermore, enhancing community relations and security will go a long way to minimizing disturbance and maximizing the dividends accruable from divestment. In fact, it is the strategic enshrined and inclusive approach to divestment that may translate potential energy benefit of this nation's oil sector into an engine for local empowerment and sustainable development in Nigeria.

Research Question Conclusions

Community Agitations and Crises

Although this was not clearly stated in AGIP's divestment plan, it was discovered that in contrast to a number of multinational oil companies divesting from onshore assets in Nigeria, there has been a decline in community agitations and crises in the Niger-Delta portion of their operations. Its ability to better understand socio-cultural dynamics makes local and national oil companies more committed to building positive relations with local communities. This has resulted in better communications, improved community engagements, and more responsive strategies for conflict resolution, culminating in a general reduction of community unrest. Although the general trend is positive, nothing succeeds singly in reducing agitations across all communities. In some areas, sporadic conflicts still occur, indicating that local conditions and the quality of national and local companies in handling relationships may help explain the varying effectiveness of divestment in managing crises. Hence, for the first research question, descriptive statistics show that the divestment of multinational oil companies from Nigerian onshore assets will reduce and possibly eliminate community agitations and crisis within the onshore areas if properly implemented.

Crude Oil Theft

The study has shown that, in some cases, divestment impacts crude oil theft in Nigeria. Some reduction in the rate of oil theft within certain locations has been reported due to better security husbandry and incentives by local-national companies that have overtaken the multinationals to secure their assets better. Most of these companies usually engage local security people who know the terrain and the local dynamics, hence developing more effective surveillance and intervention strategies. In other areas, however, the incidence of oil theft either remained or got worse. This discrepancy can be attributed to a wide variety of factors, which range from the different levels of resources available with various companies, through the presence of deeply entrenched criminal networks, to how effective government support is really in fighting theft. Be that as it may, divestment holds some potential for reduced oil theft; attainment of far-reaching reduction requires board-wide comprehensive and coordinated efforts in security and governance across all levels.

Thus, for the second research question, divestment of multinational oil companies from onshore assets will reduce oil theft incidence within the host community based on the findings of this study.

Crude Oil Production and Revenue

On crude oil production and revenues, the general finding is that national and local companies basically maintained, and in some cases, slightly improved production after divestment by the multinational corporations. The continuity and increase in production have been mainly possible because of vested interests among locals to ensure operational efficiency and maximize output. These companies often are more agile and adaptable to local conditions, which could provide for better management of production processes and lesser downtime. This divestment has also created an economic environment that is more participatory—involving local entities at the helm of affairs related

to the production and distribution of oil resources—which may lend greater transparency and accountability to revenue management.

Economically, divestment has affected present oil revenue positively for Nigeria. The local companies, by retaining production levels, have ensured the stabilizing of the revenue stream from oil. Besides, local ownership has been accompanied by a fair share of the oil revenues directly accruing to the local community and contributing towards regional economic development. The economic benefits are not, however, evenly distributed, and some regions still face challenges in benefiting fully from the opportunities, divestment presents. The broader economic implication is that national and local companies can make a decided contribution toward growth and stability in the sustainable economic development of the oil sector of Nigeria if appropriate support and regulatory frameworks are aligned.

The questions arising from the physical divestment of multinational oil companies in Nigerian onshore assets are at the same time opportunities and challenges. Among the definitely positive outcomes, which would work to enhance regional stability, are reduced community agitations and a potential decrease in crude oil theft. Noted also is that production levels are maintained, with an added positive impact on oil revenue by the economic viability of local and national companies handling such assets. However, achieving consistent success across all regions requires a strategic approach that includes robust security measures, effective community engagement, and supportive government policies.

Therefore, for the third research question, based on the findings of this study, divestment will not have any significant effect on crude oil production and oil revenue in Nigeria.

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